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ABSTRACTS

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Antibacterial and antibiofilm activities of bacteriocin produced by a new strain of *Enterococcus faecalis* BDR22

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Abstract: Antibiotic resistance generated due to rampant misuse of antibiotics and almost 80% recalcitrant bacterial pathogens are not easily treated by antibiotics due to existence of biofilm. Hence, an alternative strategy needs to be adopted so that this biofilm forming recalcitrant infectious agents can be treated without the development of antibiotic resistance. Bacteriocins, being considered as one of such therapeutic option, are the ribosome mediated proteinaceous toxins having the potential to inhibit the growth of small range of bacteria. In the present study, after screening number of sources, a bacteriocin producing strain *Enterococcus faecalis* BDR22 was isolated and identified from one dairy product that showed marked reduction (around 80%) in the growth of planktonic cells of Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC 23235) and Gram-negative *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC 10145) compared to the conventional antibiotic tetracycline in minimum concentration of 7.477 μ g/mL (w/v). The considerable reduction of the biofilm forming sessile cells with no significant cell revival even after removal of the treatment was also perceived with 87.12 $\pm$ 0.02% and 86.37 $\pm$ 0.015% reduction of *S. aureus* and *P. aeruginosa* respectively. The Extracellular Polymeric Substance content of the biofilm was also reduced with a total carbohydrate reduction of 84.78 $\pm$ 0.01% in *S. aureus* and 84.11 $\pm$ 0.007% in *P. aeruginosa*. The molecular docking interactions with docking energy Δ G of -54.40 kcal/mol and -66.2373 kcal/mol validate the affinity of the bacteriocin towards the biofilm forming protein confirming the competence of bacteriocin produced by the working strain to act as antimicrobial and antibiofilm agent against several common pathogenic bacteria replacing antibiotics.

Keywords: Bacteriocin, *Enterococcus faecalis*, antibacterial, antibiofilm, molecular docking.

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